

FAIRness assessment:

A comparison of the RDA model and the F-UJI Automated tool

Report

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Executive Summary

In this report, we present our analysis of the FAIRness of GESIS as seen from the perspective of FAIRness assessment models and tools, such as the F-UJI tool, which was recently used in the European Research Data Landscape report [1]. In summary, GESIS has systematic weaknesses. Some are unavoidable, such as the restrictions given to us through our licensing policies, some lead us to consider improving our infrastructure, such as including .csv files when available, and some are technical in nature, meaning that we have the required metadata, but they are, however, not represented in a way that the tool recognizes. It is worth pointing out that while these weaknesses are unfortunate, they do not affect users negatively in any tangible way. All the information required for findability is available to the aggregators that are relevant to us and via the web interface the way it should be. However, the research data ecosystem is constantly changing, so providing more metadata in an easily machine-readable way will likely be relevant in the future. FAIR assessment tools are valuable in giving us feedback on what to improve.

1 FAIRness assessment models

Since the FAIRⁱ concept launched in 2016 [2], coined within the FORCE11 community, scientific and scholarly institutions have widely adopted FAIR compliance principles in their research data infrastructures and services. In this sense, measuring the levels of adherence to FAIRness became necessary, mainly due to the lack of harmonization in interpreting the principles. To this end, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) set up the FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group to specify the required indicators for institutions to assess their levels of FAIR compliance. Based on the RDA Model, other initiatives proposed adapted frameworks to address the FAIR evaluation from their perspectives, incorporating different elements from community standards (i.e., metadata schema, repositories indexing, controlled vocabularies, etc.).

This report compares two frameworks, the (1) FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines (RDA-FDMM)[3] from RDA and the (2) FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics [4] used as the F-UJI Tool [5] assessment criteria. This section presents an overview of each framework and compares the indicators list to demonstrate their similarities. Section two addresses the F-UJI Tool automatic assessment results on Gesis Search, listing the issues and viable solutions followed by an action plan for improving scores. Section three demonstrates the manual assessment of da|ra using the RDA Maturity Model since this is a more comprehensive framework.

1.1 RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model

The RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model (RDA Working Group on FAIR Data Maturity Model, 2020 [3]) framework consists of 3 indicator classes: Essential, Important, and Useful. The sum of the classes is organized into five levels according to the present indicator in each category. When distributing the indicators per FAIR area, the principle of Accessibility and Interoperability holds the most Essential

ⁱ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

and Important criteria for FAIRness. Table 1 shows how these indicators are organized among the three classes and the five levels. It is necessary to pass all indicators classified as essential to achieving level 1. Achieving 50% of Important measures (minimum 7 out of 14 indicators) is necessary for the second level. Level 3 requires a completely important achievement, 14 out of 14. Level 4 adds at least 3 out of 7 indicators from the essential category. Finally, level 5 requires all seven essential indicators.

FAIR Data Maturity Model: evaluation framework		Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Essential	20	20	20	20	20	20
Important	14		7	14	14	14
Useful	7				3	7
Total	41	20	27	34	37	41

Table 1: RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model: indicators classes in five levels [6]

Each one of the FAIR principles is also an essential part of the RDA FAIR Data Maturity framework. The model distributes each class according to each FAIR principle, as shown in Table 2.

Distribution of priorities per FAIR area					
Principle	Findable	Accessible	Interoperable	Reusable	Total
Essential	7	8	0	5	20
Important	0	3	7	4	14
Useful	0	1	5	1	7
Grand Total	7	12	12	10	41

Table 2: RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model: indicators according to the FAIR Principles [6].

A list of the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model indicators is detailed in the next section, while it is compared with the F-UJI Tool assessment criteria.

1.2 The two frameworks comparison

The FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines were incorporated in the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics, which is used as F-UJI tool assessment criteria. Table 3 highlights the key facts of both frameworks. It is important to mention that the FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines provide the principles measuring each one of the FAIR principles, such as Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability. The FAIR Data Maturity Model defines a set of indicators, their priorities and evaluation methods for evaluating the FAIR principles to be used as a common approach across assessment methodologies [3].

In contrast, the goal of the F-UJI Tool is to provide an *automated* way to the FAIR assessment of research data from trustworthy data repositories. Thus, only indicators that can be assessed automatically are considered, leading to a set of just 16 out of the 41 indicators proposed by RDA.

<p>FAIRSF AIR Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe</p> <p>F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool</p>	
FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines	FAIRSF AIR Data Object Assessment Metrics used as a framework of F-UJI Tool
DOI: 10.15497/rda00050	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6461229
<p>Date</p> <p>25-06-2020</p>	<p>Date</p> <p>14-04-2022</p>
<p>Source</p> <p>FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (2020): FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines.</p>	<p>Source</p> <p>F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool</p>
<p>Framework</p> <p>Indicators: Includes 41 metrics</p> <p>Organization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizes the Indicators according to the individual aspects of FAIRness Priorities, i.e., the relative importance of the indicators (Essential, useful, and important) Provides two Evaluation methods, i.e., indicators can be evaluated by binary answers (Measuring pass-or-fail) or measuring progress. 	<p>Framework</p> <p>Indicators: Includes 16 metrics</p> <p>Organization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizes the Indicators according to the individual aspects of FAIRness
<p>Indicators</p> <p>Developed by the RDA Working Group</p>	<p>Indicators</p> <p>The framework was developed based on existing work (FAIRdat/FAIREnough, WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fit Checklist and RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model v0.03).</p> <p>Specification Link (Appendix II): https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3678715</p>

Table 3: key facts of both frameworks: FAIR Data Maturity Model X FAIRSF AIR Data Object Assessment Metrics

Both FAIR Data Maturity Model and FAIRsFAIR Data Object frameworks have a set of indicators to measure the FAIR principles, which are compared in the following. The frameworks provide indicators on the FAIR principles, including metrics for elements such as data, metadata, persistent identifiers, access, community standards and best practices for indexing, harvesting, and retrieving data and metadata. The criteria list with Metric identifiers and names is detailed in Table 4.

FAIR Data Maturity Model Specification and Guidelines		FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics used as a framework of F-UJI Tool	
Metric Identifier	Metric Name	Metric Identifier	Metric Name
RDA-F1-02D	Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	FsF-F1-01D	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.
RDA-F1-01D	Data is identified by a persistent identifier	FsF-F1-02D	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
RDA-F2-01M	Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	FsF-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary, and keywords) to support data findability .
RDA-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier for the data	FsF-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes .
RDA-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	FsF-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines .
RDA-A1-01M	Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	FsF-A1-01M	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.
RDA-A1-04M	Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	FsF-A1-02M	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
RDA-A1-04D	Data is accessible through standardised protocol	FsF-A1-03D	Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
RDA-A2-01M	Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available	FsF-A2-01M	Metadata remains available , even if the data is no longer available.
RDA-I1-01M	Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	FsF-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
RDA-I2-01M	Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	FsF-I2-01M	Metadata uses semantic resources.
RDA-I3-01M	Metadata includes references to other metadata		
RDA-I3-03M	Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata		
RDA-I3-02M	Metadata includes references to other data	FsF-I3-01M	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities .

RDA-I3-04M	Metadata includes qualified references to other data	FsF-R1-01MD	Metadata specifies the content of the data.
RDA-R1-01M	Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse (the quantity but also the quality of metadata provided to enhance data reusability.)	FsF-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused .
RDA-R1.1-02M	Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence		
RDA-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards	FsF-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
RDA-R1.3-01M	Metadata complies with a community standard	FsF-R1.3-01M	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.
RDA-R1.3-02M	Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard		
RDA-R1.3-01D	Data complies with a community standard	FsF-R1.3-02D	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community .

Table 4: FAIR Data Maturity Model X FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics: Metric identifiers and names.

Not all RDA indicators can be related to the F-UJI Metrics. Following in table 5 are the indicators foreseen in the RDA Model only.

Metric Identifier	Metric Name
RDA-F1-01M	Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier
RDA-F1-02M	Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier
RDA-A1-02M	Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e., with human intervention)
RDA-A1-02D	Data can be accessed manually (i.e., with human intervention)
RDA-A1-03M	Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record
RDA-A1-03D	Data identifier resolves to a digital object
RDA-A1.1-01M	Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol
RDA-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused
RDA-A1-05D	Data can be accessed automatically (i.e., by a computer program)
RDA-A1.1-01D	Data is accessible through a free access protocol
RDA-I1-01D	Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format
RDA-I1-02D	Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation
RDA-R1.1-03M	Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence
RDA-R1.3-02D	Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard
RDA-A1.2-01D	Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation
RDA-I2-01D	Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies
RDA-I3-01D	Data includes references to other data
RDA-I3-02D	Data includes qualified references to other data
RDA-R1.2-02M	Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language

Table 5: Indicators are only foreseen in the RDA Model, not matched with F-UJI Tool.

2 Automated assessment

The European Research Data Landscape report [1] assessed the FAIRness of datasets in repositories using the F-UJI FAIR data assessment tool. GESIS was scored in position 26 among the 31 sampled data repositories from the re3data.org registry. For each repository, up to 300 datasets were randomly selected and assessed. For each dataset, F-UJI reported the scores earned per principle based on the associated tests performed and the maximum scores attainable on the F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool [5].

Although this report analyses the F-UJI as an automatic assessment tool, other initiatives exist in this direction. Other online tools and services also allow an automatic or manual assessment of a given requirement criteria to assess the FAIRness of digital objects: FAIR Evaluation Services [7], FAIR-Checker [8], and AtMoDat Data Checker [9]. Those tools aim to evaluate the FAIRness of research data in a multidisciplinary landscape. Some resources are self-assessment tools, where the assessment is manual, providing; as a result, a score level as an output, such as the FairDataBR [10], FAIRshake [11], ARDC FAIR Self-Assessment Tool [12], SATISFYD [13], FAIR-aware [14], and the CSIRO 5-Star Data Rating Tool [15].

2.1 Automated FAIR Data Assessment at GESIS using F-UJI

The F-UJI tool assessment criteria are based on 16 of 17 core FAIR object assessment metrics developed within FAIRsFAIR [4], each corresponding to a part or the whole of FAIR principles. The results from the European Data Landscape report, while assessing the FAIRness of a dataset, it is, in fact, evaluating certain aspects of the repository holding that dataset [1]. According to the European Data Landscape report [1] (p. 35), the tool assesses the FAIRness of datasets in repositories sampling 31 data repositories, and for each repository, up to 300 datasets were randomly selected and assessed from the institution in question. However, the methodology is not detailed, for example, where the F-UJI tool collects the information from, i.e., from DataCite, R3data.org or the registered landing page of the resource. We assume that the sample datasets used for the report were found by using GESIS Search. We could easily replicate the results under this assumption, but the report is unfortunately unclear.

The F-UJI Tool takes the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of the datasets in question and tries to find metadata for it from multiple sources: DOI.org and Datacite, and also crawls the dataset's landing page. The metadata is then fused, which means that, in principle, it is sufficient to provide the information from only one source. However, some of the metadata is only extracted from some of the sources, as we learned through analysing the code. No reason is given for this, and we cannot think of any substantial reason this should be so.

Following, we address the issues on the F-UJI Tool assessment results we found in more detail. In short, the tool, which is not able to harvest metadata generated by JavaScript (JS), does not recognize the metadata provided on the landing site, although these are read fine by other aggregators, such as Google Dataset Search. Additionally, we have identified a number of issues, like providing provenance information in a specific way and providing licensing information in the recommended format rather than as free text as we currently do. Identifying what should be changed is an ongoing process, but the input received has already proven valuable.

2.1.1 Results from the F-UJI tool assessment

The F-UJI Tool took some issues with missing information on the GESIS Search landing page, but that did not lead to a point deduction (F2-01M [16]). However, there are a lot of issues with missing metadata, which, to our knowledge, is available but was not exhibited in the DataCite metadata: Table 6 lists these issues and the deducted points for each.

Requirements	Point(s) deduction
Missing proper keywords describing the dataset (incl. general keywords describing domain and scope)	1 point deduction;
Object_content_identifier that contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content is missing:	1 point deduction;
Although license information is given but not in the form of SPDX license representation (see Software Package Data Exchange (SPDX)ii License List, for example)	1.5 points deduction in two distinct categories;
No use of standardized web communication protocols such as http ⁱⁱⁱ /https ^{iv} to link to the content data	1 point deduction;
Lack of namespaces of known semantic resources that are not schema.org	1 point deduction;
Missing data content descriptors such as descriptors to describe the size and format of the data content	1 point deduction;
No use of formal provenance information ontologies such as PROV Ontology (PROV-O) to provide provenance information	1 point deduction;
Faulty Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data) entry	1 point deduction;
No OAI-PMH ^v endpoint given	1 point deduction;
We got an unavoidable 2 points deduction directly and indirectly, because GESIS data is not directly accessible due to the licensing of the data.	2 points deduction;

Table 6: Requirements x points deduction.

Thus, special attention should be paid to the use of semantic vocabularies, such as PROV-O. At least three scores could be increased by using standard options for the fields.

Table 7 presents the complete results of the assessments with F-UJI Tool and the reasons for failed indicators.

F-UJI		Assessment			
Metric Identifier	Metric Name	Comments on the assessment criteria - limitations and restrictions	Pass	Fail achieved points / maximum	Correction actions identified
FsF-F1-01D	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	It uses DOI	YES		
FsF-F1-02D	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	The PID is resolvable	YES		
FsF-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date,			1/2	The keyword is not correctly mapped

ⁱⁱ <http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/deed.de>

ⁱⁱⁱ Hypertext Transfer Protocol

^{iv} Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

^v Open Archives Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

	summary, and keywords) to support data findability.				
FsF-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	A class to evaluate whether the metadata includes the identifier of the data is being described (F3-01M). A child class of FAIREvaluator. This method will evaluate whether the metadata contains an identifier, e.g., PID or URL, which indicates the location of the downloadable data content or a data identifier that matches the identifier as part of the assessment request. (https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji/blob/master/fuji_server/client/ex_evaluate.py)		0/1	File name, size, type, and PID are missing
FsF-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.		YES		
FsF-A1-01M	Metadata contains the access level and access conditions of the data.			0.5/1	Licence should be in the SPDX registry
FsF-A1-02M	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol		n/a	n/a	
FsF-A1-03D	Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol			0/1	Not in metadata_mapper.py
FsF-A2-01M	Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.		YES		
FsF-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.			1/2	Landing page does not contain JSON-LD
FsF-I2-01M	Metadata uses semantic resources.			0/1	No known namespaces of semantic resources in the metadata
FsF-I3-01M	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.		n/a	n/a	
FsF-R1-01MD	Metadata specifies the content of the data.			1/4	File size and type are not in the metadata, two more points are unachievable due to lack of Open Access

FsF-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.			1/2	Licence not in SPDX
FsF-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.		YES		
FsF-R1.3-01M	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.			0/1	The OAI-PMH endpoint is not listed at re3data
FsF-R1.3-02D	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.			0/1	Ideally file extension .csv

Table 7: Gesis search automated assessment results: Correction actions identified.

Following is one example of how to improve the metadata description to increase the F-UJI tool's score.

2.1.1.2 Improvement of metadata based on results from F-UJI

Although the complete code of the F-UJI tool is accessible, the requirements to receive the highest score are not evident. Therefore, we evaluated the PID metadata of those datasets which received the best FAIR scores from F-UJI to use them as a template on how to improve the FAIR scores of GESIS's datasets. For this, we took the PIDs provided in the F-UJI repository. After evaluating these PIDs, we found some PIDs of datasets from Pangaea that received the highest score, which we inspected in depth. The PIDs were automatically evaluated using a Python script [See Appendix 2]. Based on the PIDs with the best performance, we updated the metadata of GESIS PIDs, using the best score of Pangaea PIDs, for example, to improve the score of GESIS PIDs.

The following methodology describes how Pangaea PIDs were used, because these PIDs got the highest scores, to find the way to address indicator **FsF-F3-01M**: "Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes". We used them as examples to replicate their structure to GESIS PIDs to get better evaluation results.

Following is the description of an example of how to address the indicator.

1. We selected a PID of Pangaea such as 10.1594/PANGAEA.896664 and used F-UJI tool to assess the PID. This PID got full score for FsF-F3-01M.
2. From the evaluation output (see item a) of F-UJI tool, we got the content identifier url: "https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896664 size and type of the data.
 - a. The content identifier url:

```
_{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
```

```

    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "4.0",
        "type": "application\zip",
        "url": "https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896664?format=zip"
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

3. We then use the information above to work out how the url/size/type were defined for the PID. In this case, we found that a Signposting link (Signposting the Scholarly Web^{vi}) (see below) was used in head of the landing page to define the url/size/type of the data.

```

<link rel="item" href="https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896664?format=zip"
type="application/zip">

```

4. We then evaluated also using Signposting links with GESIS PIDs. After successfully being able to get full score with this indicator, we know that we can use the Signposting links to address this indicator.

The procedure for other indicators is analogous. We derive some recommendations, which are presented in the next section. This list is partial, as we have not yet finished the procedure for all indicators. The test results are available in Appendix 1: results of Pre-test analysis, Test attempts and findings and the after-test recommendations. We evaluated the PIDs automatically using a Python script, available in Appendix 2. Also, the complete test attempts are available in Appendix 3: results of different attempts using the F-UJI tool in this report.

2.2 Lessons learned from using automated assessment tools

These are general recommendations and lessons learned towards increasing the scores attained through automatic tools.

1. Embed metadata in the landing page XHTML^{vii}/HTML^{viii} outside of the JavaScript
2. Download link should be a Signposting link
3. Keywords, as part of the descriptive core elements (FsF-F2-01M) should be added to the metadata field to support data findability (Keyword example: Social Science), also in all JSON-LD and schema.org. Simple classification, such as “Social Science” keyword, should suffice; keywords using more detailed controlled vocabularies would be preferable when it exists.
4. Object_content_identifier_included should be filled with file name, size, type, and URL for data download;

^{vi} <https://signposting.org/>

^{vii} EXtensible HyperText Markup Language

^{viii} Hypertext Markup Language

5. Standard_data_protocol should be “https”;
6. Linked Open Data(LOD) reference list should include a vocabulary that is datacite.org/schema, but not schema.org;
7. Data_content_descriptor is empty, should include links, file size, file type, measured variables or observation type;
8. No Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) is defined.
9. Access_condition is not in standard terms (because it is not -> should be verifiable through SPDX or another standard vocabulary);
10. Data content does match the content descriptor since the data content cannot be easily downloaded;
11. Licence is not registered at SPDX (see above No. 9);
12. No metadata standard of the repository specified in re3data;
13. R1.3-2 is not available in an open format since it is not available without registration.

Considering the FAIRness relevancy as a cornerstone for better research, a manual evaluation was conducted to demonstrate that, apart from an automatic assessment which runs only on specific machine-friendly requirements, the FAIR principles are embedded at Gesis Services. To this end, we assessed da|ra service as requested, according to the RDA FAIR Model, which results are described in the next section.

3 The manual assessment

Although automated assessment saves effort, not all components of the research data ecosystem are machine-readable. Some aspects specified in FAIR principles still require human mediation and interpretation [17]. In this sense, our approach was conducting a manual analysis to maturity level assessment, relying on the RDA recommendation FAIR Data Maturity Model. One of the RDA FAIR maturity level assessment methodologies is the stricter evaluation method on each indicator, assessing them by passing or failing binary answers, as demonstrated in table 8.

Measuring pass-or-fail	
Present	Not present
Pass	Fail

Table 8: Measuring pass-or-fail method

We assessed the da|ra under the FAIR Data Maturity Model applying the stricter evaluation method on each indicator, assessing them manually by passing or failing binary answers. The results are demonstrated below.

3.2 Results

The **da|ra** service meets all indicators classified as **essential**. The indicator classes which do not meet the measures were four from each **important** and **useful** classified category. However, it is essential to highlight the failed indicators concerned with automatic features, including references and/or qualified references to other data, and data is accessed automatically (i.e., by a computer program). The results are presented according to indicator per category in table 9.

The **da|ra** service passed 33 and failed eight indicators among the three categories under the RDA framework.

FAIR Data Maturity Model: assessment		
	Pass	Fail
Essential	20	0
Important	10	4
Useful	3	4
Total	33	8

Table 9: **da|ra** service assessment results

The RDA Model organizes the indicators into five classes according to the number of passed indicators. The **da|ra** results demonstrated in table 10 for each level in this model were in the range of 80% up to 100%. The **da|ra manual** assessment results demonstrate outstanding achievements at levels 1 and 2, marking 100% on the assessment measure. The service achieves 88% compliance at level 3 and 89% at level 4. At level 5, the results show 80% of passed indicators.

Framework	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
<i>Essential</i>	20 / 20	20 / 20	20 / 20	20 / 20	20 / 20
<i>Important</i>		7 / 7	10 / 14	10 / 14	10 / 14
<i>Useful</i>				3 / 3	3 / 7
Achieved indicators	20/20	27 / 27	30 / 34	33 / 37	33 / 41
Scored	20	27	30	33	33
Results	100%	100%	88%	89%	80%

Table 10: **da|ra** service assessment results: level distribution

In conclusion:

- The results demonstrate outstanding achievements at levels 1 and 2, marking 100% on the assessment measure;
- The service achieves 88% compliance at level 3 and 89% at level 4. At level 5, the results show 80% of passed indicators;
- The service meets all indicators classified as essential;

- The failed indicators concerned with automatic features, including references and/or qualified references to other data, and data is accessed automatically (i.e., by a computer program).

Figure 1: da|ra service assessment results

To assure analysis transparency, each indicator is listed in the following subsection, providing comments and evidence to ground the passed or failed indicator.

3.2.1 Detailed evidences

Detailed evidence on **Essential** indicators:

<i>FAIR RDA Data Maturity Model: criteria framework</i>	<i>Pass</i>	<i>Fail</i>	<i>Evidence</i>	<i>Comments</i>	<i>Data level</i>
RDA-F1-01M Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier	✓		It has a variable PID assigned	Metadata and data are identified via DOI	Study & in future variable level
RDA-F1-01D Data is identified by a persistent identifier	✓		It has a variable PID assigned	Metadata and data are identified via DOI	Study & in future variable level
RDA-F1-02M Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	✓		Handle standard provides globally unique identifier	Metadata and data are identified via DOI	Study & in future variable level
RDA-F1-02D Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	✓		Handle standard provides globally unique identifier	Metadata and data are identified via DOI	Study & in future variable level

RDA-F2-01M Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	✓		A metadata scheme is present to comply with the minimum metadata	Metadata is documented in DDI Lifecycle 3.2	Study & in future variable level
RDA-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier for the data	✓		It includes the DOI of the study in which the variable to register appears	The DOI is part of the metadata	Study & in future variable level
RDA-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	✓		The metadata is in fact harvested and indexed at Gesis Search and/or other institutional repository as a service user	Metadata can be harvested via OAI-PMH	Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-02M Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e., with human intervention)	✓		The metadata can be accessed with human intervention via landing page		Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-02D Data can be accessed manually (i.e., with human intervention)	✓		Access to the digital object can be obtained through human intervention, for example, accessing the Study DOI and the download button		Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-03M Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	✓		The resolution delivers the correct metadata record available at the landing page		Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-03D Data identifier resolves to a digital object	✓		The mechanism specific to the protocol (e.g., HTTP) and verifies that this delivers the digital object. The variables and/or the complete dataset		Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-04M Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	✓		Common metadata access protocols are HTTP and FTP, Atom19, OAI-PMH20 and Web Services Metadata Exchange	The metadata is accessible via OAI-PMH in standardised metadata formats (DDI CB, DDI-LC 3.2 and also Dublin Core)	Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-04D Data is accessible through standardised protocol	✓		Common data access protocols are HTTP and FTP, DAP22 and JSON-RPC	Data can be downloaded via HTTP on	Study & in future variable level

				search.gesis.org by a user.	
RDA-A1.1-01M Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	✓		What is the basis of information provided about whether the use of the protocol is free of charge. Common examples are HTTP and FTP		Study & in future variable level
RDA-A2-01M Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available	✓		The end-user can expect all necessary functionality and reliable service since a stable PID infrastructure supports the third-party (ePIC API) registration service. The registration service complies with high-quality requirements and policies under which PIDs are maintained and an SLA that standardises the ePIC services guaranteeing its continuation		Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1-01M Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse (the quantity but also the quality of metadata provided to enhance data reusability.)	✓		Minimum metadata schema: Study DOI Variable Name Variable Label PID Proposal Landing Page Resource type Title Creators Publisher Publication date Availability Description/ Abstract Concept Classification Version	DDI Metadata Schema used by GESIS.	Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.1-01M Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused	✓		Look in the metadata for licence information. Check if this info is in the Study Metadata. It is not present in the minimum schema.	Availability is clearly described in the metadata of GESIS	Study & in future variable level

RDA-R1.3-01M Metadata complies with a community standard	✓		Complies with DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)		Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.3-01D Data complies with a community standard	✓			For GESIS Data, most is available in SPSS, STATA (also community standard, but proprietary)	Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.3-02M Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	✓		Metadata has a machine-understandable expression		Study & in future variable level

Table 11: da|ra service assessment: detailed evidence on essential indicators

Detailed evidence on **important** indicators:

<i>FAIR RDA Data Maturity Model: criteria framework</i>	<i>Pass</i>	<i>Fail</i>	<i>Evidence</i>	<i>Comments</i>	<i>Data level</i>
RDA-A1-01M Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	✓		Provide information on (i) access conditions according to the metadata standard used, (ii) information that describes the actions to be taken and for example on a landing page of the digital object or (iii) the requirements to be satisfied in order to gain access to the data. The data can be accessed through the human intervention, for example, by accessing the Study DOI and the download button.	Access level in the metadata	Study & in future variable level
RDA-A1-05D Data can be accessed automatically (i.e., by a computer program)		✗	The same PID can be used to provide data access. As an example, access in R can be given to data of a variable by using the same PID as cited: variable <- read.csv("https://access.gesis.org/data?pid=10.4232/1.13737&type=variable&fileType=csv")	This is future work and independent of TA5.M1	Future service, PID service is a precondition for cross-institute access
RDA-A1.1-01D Data is accessible through a free access protocol	✓		The protocol is free of charge, the protocol used is HTTP		Future service, PID service is a precondition for cross-institute access

RDA-I1-01M Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	✓		Metadata values are expressed using controlled vocabularies - appropriateness of the knowledge representation	Da ra provides the metadata only in data XML or JSON-old. DDI is only available from special OAI-PMH endpoint	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I1-01D Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	✓		Information about the data model and format, verifying that the standard used is appropriate for the domain and the type of digital object. In this case, Statistics files are used within the Social Sciences domain. Regarding data type, a variable is embedded within a Social Science questionnaire and overall, a study or survey.	SPSS/STATA/CSV	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I1-02M Metadata uses machine-understand knowledge representation	✓		Look at the knowledge representation model used for the expression of the metadata. Examples are RDF, OWL, JSON-LD and SKOS.	Da ra provides the metadata only in data XML or JSON-old. DDI is only available from special OAI-PMH endpoint	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I1-02D Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation		✗	Look at the knowledge representation model used for the expression of the data. Examples are RDF, OWL, JSON-LD, Data Cube, the Generalized Data Model for clinical research and SKOS.	Data can be used in R/SPSS/STATA, i.e., formats used by our community	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I2-01M Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies		✗	Verify that each of the vocabularies used in the metadata is documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers, with the documentation being easily findable and accessible.		Study & in future variable level
RDA-I3-01M Metadata includes references to other metadata	✓		Look at the occurrence of references to other metadata, for example, ORCID for people or Geonames for places, ROR for Institutions		Study & in future variable level
RDA-I3-03M Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata	✓		A variable must be related to a study, a resource type, e.g., a dataset, and identifying variables information such as name and label is mandatory to obtain a PID from the registration service		Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.1-02M Metadata refers to a	✓		Verify that the licence is indeed a standard licence. Examples of standard licences are: Creative	GESIS has a specific license	Study & in future variable level

standard reuse licence			Commons licences and Open Data Commons. Check within the Study level		
RDA-R1.1-03M Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence		✗	An example of such a machine-understandable expression is the RDF expression of Creative Commons licences or the various serialisations of the Open Data Rights Language (ODRL).	Metadata is licensed in CC0 but not expressed in machine-readable way	Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards	✓		information about provenance of the data, i.e., information about the origin, history or workflow that generated the data.	Provenance within DDI	Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.3-02D Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	✓		Verify that the community standard used, or the data has a machine-understandable expression	SSPS Stata	Study & in future variable level

Table 12: da|ra service assessment: detailed evidence on important indicators

Detailed evidence on **useful** indicators:

FAIR RDA Data Maturity Model: criteria framework	Pass	Fail	Evidence	Comments	Data level
RDA-A1.2-01D Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	✓		Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	Access to the service is provided via token-based authorization, the user needs to authenticate via the /api/register/auth endpoint beforehand.	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I2-01D Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies		✗	Verify that each of the vocabularies used in the data is documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers, with the documentation being easily findable and accessible	CV included in Da ra metadata schema (https://doi.org/10.4232/10.mdsdo.c.4.0). in some cases, we have two similar fields, one employing a	Study & in future variable level

				CV and in additional free-text field (e.g., "rights"), which might cause trouble when information is crappie automatically.	
RDA-I3-01D Data includes references to other data		✗	Presence of references to other data in data. For example, there may be links to other resources in cells in a spreadsheet or in RDF-based data.	Policy in the data archive	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I3-02M Metadata includes references to other data.	✓		Metadata is connected to other data, for example linking to previous or related research data that provides additional context to the data.	There are "alternative IDs" and "related IDs"	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I3-02D Data includes qualified references to other data		✗	Validating the presence of references with the specification of the relationship role that the related resource has with the data object. The references need to be qualified, which means that the relationship role of the related resource is specified, for example, that a particular link is a specification of a unit of measurement	Information that must be provided by data depository	Study & in future variable level
RDA-I3-04M Metadata include qualified references to other data	✓		The relationship role of the related resource is specified, for example, dataset X is derived from dataset Y.		Study & in future variable level
RDA-R1.2-02M Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language		✗	Assess whether a cross-domain language is used for provenance information (such as PROV-O).	Provenance fields like "creator" based on schema.org (see JSON-LD)	Study & in future variable level

Table 13: da|ra service assessment: detailed evidence on useful indicators

4 Conclusion

Conducting an assessment is a good practice to comply with cornerstone principles such as FAIR to better research. The RDA Maturity Model is the lead framework due to its completeness and comprehensive acknowledgement from the community and specialists. This model is an RDA Working Group output, and most automatic or hybrid assessment tools rely partially on its indicators and measures. The in-depth FAIR analysis using RDA-FDMM helped us better understand where our services stand with regards to FAIR, whereas the F-UJI tool gave us valuable hints on how to improve our metadata, despite the fact that automated tools always have limitations and technical challenges. Our experience with RDA-FDMM and the F-UJI tool highlights the importance of evaluating both machine-readable as well as non-machine-readable elements. In future work, we recommend considering other FAIR assessment tools (such as the examples in section 2), including manual assessment through the RDA-FDMM since it is broadly recognized by the FAIR community.

Regarding the GESIS internal processes, an approach such as “FAIR by design” should be adopted at the beginning of each product and services development. FAIR by Design aims to align research data infrastructures with FAIR principles through their entire lifecycle. Regular FAIR assessments and continuous improvements in FAIR scores should become an integral part of any data infrastructure development. Embracing a set of audit measures from the FAIR standpoint in advance would lead GESIS to a proactive policy in terms of FAIRness. Other Gesis data sources could also be considered to be assessed in the future.

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Appendix 1: Analysis, Test Findings and Recommendations

A) Pre-test analysis

- I. In the Pangaea landing page <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.896664>, the following link element is used to define the linked data


```
<link rel="item"
      href="https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896664?format=zip" type="application/zip">
```
- II. In Pangaea size/type are defined in the landing page in the embedded Json-LD in `<script type="application/ld+json">` using the attributes: "size" and "distribution";
- III. We tried to replicate it for GESIS DOIs as to the approach used by Pangaea. For defining linked data, we analysed the Pangaea PID landing page and applied the same approach as Pangaea to define the linked data.

B) Test attempts and findings

- I. We made 12 attempts in total, which are documented (screenshots of achieved scores in [Appendix 3: results of different attempts using the F-UJI tool](#));
- II. In the attempts, we used different landing pages (different in: 1. Link element and 2. embedded JSON-LD) for the DOI: 10.4232/1.1305, https://<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doip/fuji/XXX/10.4232/1.1305^{ix}, XXX can be 1 to 12; for example, the landing page for attempt 1 is https://<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doip/fuji/1/10.4232/1.1305^x and the landing page for attempt 2 is https://<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doip/fuji/2/10.4232/1.1305^{xi} and so on.
- III. The best score is 79 from the last attempt with landing page 12 [xii]: https://<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doip/fuji/12/10.4232/1.1305;

NOTE: if you open the above link for landing page 12, the browser will display a blank page. This is because the defined Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is NOT available on the <anonymous_server> DOIP server. However, the contents are there, and the machine can read them.

- IV. The following compares the scores of landing page 12, i.e. https://<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doip/fuji/12/10.4232/1.1305, with the scores of the origin landing page: [Landing page 12](#) is the 12th landing page created for the PID. This landing page gets the best score.

^{ix} url not working for security reasons

^x url not working for security reasons

^{xi} url not working for security reasons

^{xii} See annex 2 for information on the scores of the landing pages

V. The following are changes in landing page 12 compared with the original landing page:

- a) Landing page 12 does not compress JavaScript (JS). The F-UJI tool has the problem reading compressed JS;
- b) a link element is added for the linked date;

```
<link rel="item"
href="https://<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doip/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305" type="application/json">
```

Notes:

- i. the linked data should be accessible directly, i.e., no authorization required;
 - ii. it should not exceed 1000000 bytes; otherwise, a warning will be issued.
- c) The following elements are added to the embedded JsonLD, i.e., `<script id="dynamicJSONLD" type="application/ld+json">` to define size/type and also additionally for access level

```
“size”: {
  “@type”: “QuantitativeValue”,
  “value”: 14283,
  “unitText”: “data points”
},
“distribution”: {
  “@type”: “DataDownload”,
  “encodingFormat”: “text/plain”,
  “contentUrl”:
https://<anonymous\_server>.gesis.org/doip/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
},
“license”: https://search.gesis.org/research\_data/ZA1305,
“conditionsOfAccess”: “unrestricted”,
“isAccessibleForFree”: true
```

Notes:

- i. Size -> "value" needs to be correct, i.e., value equals to the bytes of the linked data;
- ii. Type -> "encodingFormat" needs to be correct i.e., "text/plain" for Json and text/tsv for tab-separated-data, etc;
- iii. Defining access condition using "conditionsOfAccess" and "isAccessibleForFree" gains even more score.

C) The after-test recommendations

- I. Added attribute size/format in "Optional Properties" in DataCite (<https://doi.datacite.org/doi/10.4232%2F1.1305/edit>) has no effect on FsF-F3-01M. Code tracing found that these two attributes are NOT used by F-UJI for FsF-F3-01M;
- II. In the F-UJI tool (running on a local developing environment), after disabling all the external metadata sources except DataCite / all the external data sources (including DataCite), However, DOIs from PANGAEA can still get the full score for FsF-F3-01M;
- III. Changed DATACITE_JSON_MAPPING for size/format in metadata_mapper.py in the local F-UJI tool, but it had no effect on FsF-F3-01M;
- IV. compared DataCite JSON/Schema.org JSON-LD of Pangaea DOIs and Gesis DOIs. They both had size/format defined in "Optional Properties". There is no significant difference in terms of contained attributes;
- V. Testing together with code tracing step by step found the following:
 - a) F-UJI metadata harvester issues warning on GESIS DOIs: "WARNING: Landing page seems to be JavaScript generated, could not detect enough content". However, Pangaea DOIs do not receive this kind of warning;
 - b) Pangaea checks <link> element with attribute rel="item" on the landing page to find linked data information for FsF-F3-01M;
 - c) Size and type of the linked data are defined in the "size" and "distribution" attributes of the embedded JsonLD in `<script type="application/ld+json">` in the landing page;
 - d) access level can be defined by attributes "conditionsOfAccess" and "isAccessibleForFree" in the embedded JsonLD.
- VI. Detailed recommendations can be found summarised below:
 - a) Do not compress JS;
 - b) Add element `<link ref="item" href="xx" type="xxx">` in header to define linked data;
 - c) Add attributes: "size" and "distribution" in the embedded JsonLD to define the size and type of the linked data;
 - d) Add attributes: "conditionsOfAccess" and "isAccessibleForFree" in the embedded JsonLD to define the access level to gain a better score.

Appendix 2: Python Script used to test PIDs

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-

import configparser as ConfigParser
import json
import os
import tracemalloc
from pathlib import Path
from fuji_server.controllers.fair_check import FAIRCheck
from fuji_server.helper.catalogue_helper_google_datasearch import
MetaDataCatalogueGoogleDataSearch
from fuji_server.helper.preprocessor import Preprocessor
import gc
import sys
# os
#os.environ['TIKA_SERVER_JAR'] = 'file://Program Files\tika\tika-server-1.24.1.jar'

identifier = 'https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902845'

debug = True
muchotestpids = []
startpid = ""
testpids=['https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.896660', 'https://meta.icos-
cp.eu/objects/EIEL6bM9CNOXMP5ZxLxKots5', 'https://www.health-atlas.de/data_files/21']

mypids = {}
compare_scores = []
print(len(testpids))
startpid=""
metadata_service_endpoint = ""
metadata_service_type = ""
oaipmh_endpoint = ""
```

```
def effectivehandlers(logger):
    handlers = logger.handlers
    while True:
        logger = logger.parent
        handlers.extend(logger.handlers)
        if not (logger.parent and logger.propagate):
            break
    return handlers

def main():
    config = ConfigParser.ConfigParser()
    my_path = Path(__file__).parent.parent
    ini_path = os.path.join(my_path, 'config', 'server.ini')
    config.read(ini_path)
    YAML_DIR = config['SERVICE']['yaml_directory']
    METRIC_YAML = config['SERVICE']['metrics_yaml']
    METRIC_YML_PATH = os.path.join(my_path, YAML_DIR, METRIC_YAML)
    SPDX_URL = config['EXTERNAL']['spdx_license_github']
    DATACITE_API_REPO = config['EXTERNAL']['datacite_api_repo']
    RE3DATA_API = config['EXTERNAL']['re3data_api']
    METADATACATALOG_API = config['EXTERNAL']['metadata_catalog']
    isDebug = config.getboolean('SERVICE', 'debug_mode')
    data_files_limit = int(config['SERVICE']['data_files_limit'])
    metric_specification = config['SERVICE']['metric_specification']
    remote_log_host = config['SERVICE'].get('remote_log_host')
    remote_log_path = config['SERVICE'].get('remote_log_path')

    #f = open("test_fujipids_ab_4001_result.txt", "w")
    print('starting ...')
    #print to a file.
    #sys.stdout = f
    preproc = Preprocessor()
    preproc.retrieve_metrics_yaml(METRIC_YML_PATH, data_files_limit, metric_specification)
```

```
print(f'Total metrics defined: {preproc.get_total_metrics()}')
#print(f'Total metrics defined: {preproc.get_total_metrics()}', file="testIds_results.txt")
isDebug = config.getboolean('SERVICE', 'debug_mode')
preproc.retrieve_licenses(SPDX_URL, isDebug)
preproc.retrieve_datacite_re3repos(RE3DATA_API, DATACITE_API_REPO, isDebug)
preproc.retrieve_metadata_standards(METADATACATALOG_API, isDebug)
preproc.retrieve_science_file_formats(isDebug)
preproc.retrieve_long_term_file_formats(isDebug)
preproc.set_remote_log_info(config['SERVICE'].get('remote_log_host'),
config['SERVICE'].get('remote_log_path'))
preproc.set_max_content_size(config['SERVICE']['max_content_size'])
print(f'Total SPDX licenses : {preproc.get_total_licenses()}')
#f.write(f'Total SPDX licenses : {preproc.get_total_licenses()}')
print(f'Total re3repositories found from datacite api : {len(preproc.getRE3repositories())}')
#f.write(f'Total re3repositories found from datacite api : {len(preproc.getRE3repositories())}')
print(f'Total subjects area of imported metadata standards : {len(preproc.metadata_standards)}')
#f.write(f'Total subjects area of imported metadata standards :
{len(preproc.metadata_standards)}')
start = False
usedatacite = True
n = 1
for identifier in testpids:
    results = []
    ft = None
    tracemalloc.start()
    print(identifier)
    print(n)
    n += 1
    if identifier == startpid or not startpid:
        start = True
    if start:
        ft = FAIRCheck(uid=identifier,
            test_debug=debug,
            metadata_service_url=metadata_service_endpoint,
            metadata_service_type=metadata_service_type,
```

```
        use_datacite=usedatacite,
        oaipmh_endpoint=oaipmh_endpoint)

#ft = FAIRCheck(uid=identifier, test_debug=True, use_datacite=usedatacite)
#set target for remote logging
#if remote_log_host and remote_log_path:
# ft.set_remote_logging_target(remote_log_host, remote_log_path)

uid_result, pid_result = ft.check_unique_persistent()
ft.retrieve_metadata_embedded()
if ft.repeat_pid_check:
    uid_result, pid_result = ft.check_unique_persistent()
include_embedded = True
ft.retrieve_metadata_external()
if ft.repeat_pid_check:
    uid_result, pid_result = ft.check_unique_persistent()
core_metadata_result = ft.check_minimal_metatadata()
content_identifier_included_result = ft.check_content_identifier_included()
access_level_result = ft.check_data_access_level()
license_result = ft.check_license()
related_resources_result = ft.check_relatedresources()
check_searchable_result = ft.check_searchable()
data_content_result = ft.check_data_content_metadata()
data_file_format_result = ft.check_data_file_format()
community_standards_result = ft.check_community_metadastandards()
data_provenance_result = ft.check_data_provenance()
formal_metadata_result = ft.check_formal_metadata()
semantic_vocab_result = ft.check_semantic_vocabulary()
metadata_preserved_result = ft.check_metadata_preservation()
standard_protocol_data_result = ft.check_standardised_protocol_data()
standard_protocol_metadata_result = ft.check_standardised_protocol_metadata()

results.append(uid_result)
results.append(pid_result)
```

```
results.append(core_metadata_result)
results.append(content_identifier_included_result)
results.append(check_searchable_result)
results.append(access_level_result)
results.append(formal_metadata_result)
results.append(semantic_vocab_result)
results.append(related_resources_result)
results.append(data_content_result)
results.append(license_result)
results.append(data_provenance_result)
results.append(community_standards_result)
results.append(data_file_format_result)
results.append(standard_protocol_data_result)
results.append(standard_protocol_metadata_result)
#print(ft.metadata_merged)
debug_messages = ft.get_log_messages_dict()
#ft.logger_message_stream.flush()
summary = ft.get_assessment_summary(results)
#
print(summary)
#f.write(summary)
print('score: ', summary.get('score_percent').get('FAIR'))
#f.write('score: ', summary.get('score_percent').get('FAIR'))
compare_scores.append(summary.get('score_percent').get('FAIR'))
for res_k, res_v in enumerate(results):
    if ft.isDebug:
        debug_list = debug_messages.get(res_v['metric_identifier'])
        #debug_list= ft.msg_filter.getMessage(res_v['metric_identifier'])
        if debug_list is not None:
            results[res_k]['test_debug'] = debug_messages.get(res_v['metric_identifier'])
        else:
            results[res_k]['test_debug'] = ['INFO: No debug messages received']
    else:
        results[res_k]['test_debug'] = ['INFO: Debugging disabled']
```

```
    debug_messages = {}
    print(json.dumps(results, indent=4, sort_keys=True))
    #f.write(json.dumps(results, indent=4, sort_keys=True))
    #print(json.dumps([core_metadata_result], indent=4, sort_keys=True))
    #remove unused logger handlers and filters to avoid memory leaks
    ft.logger.handlers = [ft.logger.handlers[-1]]
    #ft.logger.filters = [ft.logger.filters]
    current, peak = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
    #print(f"Current memory usage is {current / 10 ** 6}MB; Peak was {peak / 10 ** 6}MB")
    snapshot = tracemalloc.take_snapshot()
    top_stats = snapshot.statistics('traceback')

    # pick the biggest memory block
    stat = top_stats[0]
    #print("%s memory blocks: %.1f KiB" % (stat.count, stat.size / 1024))
    for line in stat.traceback.format():
        print(line)

    #for i, stat in enumerate(snapshot.statistics('filename')[5], 1):
    #    print(i, str(stat))
    results=[]
    #preproc.logger.
    gc.collect()
    tracemalloc.stop()
    print(compare_scores)
    #f.write(compare_scores)
    #print(comparepids.values())
    #f.write(comparepids.values())
    #f.close()

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()
```

Appendix 3: Results of different attempts using the F-UJI tool

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	(JSON)
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	4 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

- ✔️ ⌵
FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.
- ✔️ ⌵
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
- ✔️ ⌵
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
- ✔️ ⬆️
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "profile": null,
        "rel": "item",
        "source": "signposting",
        "type": "application/csv",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.gesis.org/r"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔️
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔️

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) :- 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found :- 1

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	JSON
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	5 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✓	∨
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✓	∨
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✓	∨
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✓	∧

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "500.0",
        "type": "application/csv",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.gesis.org/v/"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✓
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✓

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved programmatically.	✓	∨
---	---	---

FAIR level: 2 of 3

moderate

Score: 2 of 4

Output:

```
{
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "application\/csv",
      "matches_content": false
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "500.0",
      "matches_content": false
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.geis.org/research_data/ZA5667&ttype=CSV
WARNING	File too large., skipped download after -:10 sec or receiving > 1000000- https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.geis.org/research_data/ZA5667&ttype=CSV
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKA
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Successfully parsed data file(s) -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.geis.org/research_data/ZA5667&ttype=CSV
WARNING	Could not verify content type from downloaded file -: (expected: application/csv, found: ['text/tsv'])
WARNING	Could not verify content size from downloaded file -: (expected: 500.0, found: None)
WARNING	NO measured variables found in metadata, skip 'measured_variable' test.
WARNING	Measured variables given in metadata do not match data object content

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	[JSON]
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	5 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✓	▼
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✓	▼
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✓	▼
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✓	▲

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```
Output: {
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "500.0",
        "type": "application\\csv",
        "url": "https:\\\\www.<anonymous_server>.gegis.org\\fdoservices\\invoke\\FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https:\\\\search.gegis.org\\r"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✓
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✓

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

Wachsende Disharmonien zwischen staatlichem Leistungsangebot und gesellschaftlicher Nachfrage

Save JSON New

FAIR level: ?	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	JSON
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	4 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	▼
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	▼
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	▼
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	▲

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "profile": null,
        "rel": "item",
        "source": "signposting",
        "type": "type=\\application\\csv\\",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.gesis.org/r"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FAIR level:	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	[JSON]
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	4 of 10	initial

Report:

Findable

- FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. ✔
- FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier. ✔
- FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability. ✔
- FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. ✔

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```
Output: {
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "500.0",
        "type": "application/csv",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/dbk/4232"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔

Level:	Message:
INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1
WARNING	Content identifier inaccessible - https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/dbk/4232, HTTPError code 401

FAIR level: ?	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	JSON
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:		Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	○	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	○	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	○	initial
Reusable:	3 of 10	○	initial

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✓	▼
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✓	▼
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✓	▼
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✓	▲

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```
Output: {
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "profile": null,
        "rel": "item",
        "source": "signposting",
        "type": "application/csv",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gegis.org/dbk/42432"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✓
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✓

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1
	WARNING	Content identifier inaccessible -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.gegis.org/dbk/42432, HTTPError code 401

FAIR level: 0 of 3

incomplete

Score: 0 of 1

Output:

```
[
  {
    "file_uri": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/dbk/42432",
    "is_preferred_format": false,
    "mime_type": "application/csv",
    "preference_reason": [],
    "subject_areas": []
  },
  {
    "file_uri": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/dbk/42432",
    "is_preferred_format": false,
    "mime_type": "",
    "preference_reason": [],
    "subject_areas": []
  }
]
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1.3-02D-1	The format of a data file given in the metadata is listed in the long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file formats controlled list			
a	The format of the data file is an open format			
b	The format of the data file is a long term format			
c	The format of the data file is a scientific format			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
WARNING	Content identifier inaccessible -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/dbk/42432, HTTPError code 401
INFO	Data content identifier provided -: ['https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/dbk/42432']

FAIR level: ?	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	(JSON)
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	5 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✔
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✔
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✔
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✔

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "1130434",
        "type": "text/tsv",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/fdosservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.gesis.org/r"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FAIR level: 2 of 3

moderate

Score: 2 of 4

```

Output:
{
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "text\\t\\sv",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "1130434",
      "matches_content": false
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}

```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doip/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.geis.org/research_data/ZA1221&type=CSV
WARNING	File too large., skipped download after -:10 sec or receiving > 1000000-https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doip/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.geis.org/research_data/ZA1221&type=CSV
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKA
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Successfully parsed data file(s) - :https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doip/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_GET_RAW_DATA?pid=https://search.geis.org/research_data/ZA1221&type=CSV
WARNING	Could not verify content size from downloaded file -: (expected: 1130434, found: None)
WARNING	NO measured variables found in metadata, skip 'measured_variable' test.
WARNING	Measured variables given in metadata do not match data object content

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	{JSON}
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	5 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

- FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. ✔️ ⌵
- FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier. ✔️ ⌵
- FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability. ✔️ ⌵
- FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. ✔️ ⬆️

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```
Output: {
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "14284",
        "type": "application/json",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=10.4232/1.1305"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔️
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔️

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 2 of 3

moderate

Score: 2 of 4

```
Output: {
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "application/json",
      "matches_content": false
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "14284",
      "matches_content": false
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed - : https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKA
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Successfully parsed data file(s) -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
WARNING	Could not verify content type from downloaded file -: (expected: application/json, found: [text/plain])
WARNING	Could not verify content size from downloaded file -: (expected: 14284, found: 14283)
WARNING	NO measured variables found in metadata, skip 'measured_variable' test.
WARNING	Measured variables given in metadata do not match data object content

FsF-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.

FsF-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.

FsF-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	(JSON)
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	6 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

- FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. ✔
- FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier. ✔
- FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability. ✔
- FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. ✔

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```
Output: {
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "14283",
        "type": "text/plain",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=10.4232/1.1305"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 3 of 3 advanced

Score: 3 of 4

```
Output: {
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "text/plain",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "14283",
      "matches_content": true
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata	1	3	
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKA
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Successfully parsed data file(s) -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
WARNING	NO measured variables found in metadata, skip 'measured_variable' test.
WARNING	Measured variables given in metadata do not match data object content

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	(JSON)
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	6 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

- ✔ ▼
 FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.
- ✔ ▼
 FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
- ✔ ▼
 FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
- ✔ ▲
 FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "14283",
        "type": "text/plain",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gegis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=10.4232/1.1305"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔
FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 3 of 3 advanced

Score: 3 of 4

```
Output: {
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "text/plain",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "14283",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "measured_variable",
      "descriptor_value": "myvariable",
      "matches_content": false
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata	1	3	
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.gegis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKA
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Succesfully parsed data file(s) -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.gegis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
SUCCESS	Found measured variables or observations (aka parameters) as content descriptor
WARNING	Measured variables given in metadata do not match data object content

FAIR level: ⓘ	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	[JSON]
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	2.5 of 3	moderate
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	7 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

- FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. ✔
- FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier. ✔
- FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability. ✔
- FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. ✔

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```
Output: {
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "14283",
        "type": "text/plain",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=10.4232/1.1305"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✔
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✔

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/ld+json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 3 of 3

advanced

Score: 4 of 4

```
Output: {
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "text/plain",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "14283",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "measured_variable",
      "descriptor_value": "Gemeinde, Wohnungsbau, Stadtleben und Landleben",
      "matches_content": true
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	✓
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			✓
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			✓
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	✓
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			✓
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			✓
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata	1	3	✓
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata	1	3	✓

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKa
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Successfully parsed data file(s) -: https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
SUCCESS	Found measured variables or observations (aka parameters) as content descriptor
SUCCESS	Found specified measured variable in data object content

FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data. ✓ ^

FAIR level: 1 of 3 initial

Score: 0.5 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "access_details": {
    "access_condition": "Alle im GESIS DBK ver\u00f6ffentlichen Metadaten sind frei verf\u00fcbgbar unter den Creative Commons CC0",
  },
  "access_level": null
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-A1-01M-1	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	0.5	1	✓
FsF-A1-01M-2	Data access information is machine readable			?
FsF-A1-01M-3	Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms			?

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Access information specified -: Alle im GESIS DBK ver\u00f6ffentlichen Metadaten sind frei verf\u00fcbgbar unter den Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication. GESIS bittet jedoch darum, dass Sie alle Metadatenquellen anerkennen und sie nennen, etwa die Datengeber oder jeglichen Aggregator, inklusive GESIS selbst. F\u00fcr weitere Informationen siehe https://dbk.gesis.org/dbksearch/guidelines.asp?db=d
INFO	Verify name through SPDX registry -: Alle im GESIS DBK ver\u00f6ffentlichen Metadaten sind frei verf\u00fcbgbar unter den Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication. GESIS bittet jedoch darum, dass Sie alle Metadatenquellen anerkennen und sie nennen, etwa die Datengeber oder jeglichen Aggregator, inklusive GESIS selbst. F\u00fcr weitere Informationen siehe https://dbk.gesis.org/dbksearch/guidelines.asp?db=d
INFO	Access information specified -: All metadata from GESIS DBK are available free of restriction under the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication. However, GESIS requests that you actively acknowledge and give attribution to all metadata sources, such as the data providers and any data aggregators, including GESIS. For further information see https://dbk.gesis.org/dbksearch/guidelines.asp
INFO	Verify name through SPDX registry -: All metadata from GESIS DBK are available free of restriction under the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication. However, GESIS requests that you actively acknowledge and give attribution to all metadata sources, such as the data providers and any data aggregators, including GESIS. For further information see https://dbk.gesis.org/dbksearch/guidelines.asp
INFO	Found access rights information in dedicated metadata element
WARNING	Unable to determine the access level

FAIR level: ?	moderate
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	(JSON)
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:	Fair level:
Findable:	7 of 7	advanced
Accessible:	3 of 3	advanced
Interoperable:	2 of 4	initial
Reusable:	7 of 10	moderate

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	✓	▼
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	✓	▼
FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	✓	▼
FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	✓	▲

FAIR level: 3 of 3 **advanced**

Score: 1 of 1

```

Output:
{
  "object_content_identifier_included": [
    {
      "content_identifier_included": {
        "size": "14283",
        "type": "text/plain",
        "url": "https://www.<anonymous_server>.gesis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=10.4232/1.1305"
      }
    }
  ]
}
    
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5	1	✓
	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	0.5	3	✓

Debug messages:	Level:	Message:
	INFO	Found data links in application/json metadata -: 1
	INFO	Found data links in HTML head (link rel=item) -: 1
	SUCCESS	Number of object content identifier found -: 1

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 3 of 3

advanced

Score: 4 of 4

Output:

```
{
  "data_content_descriptor": [
    {
      "descriptor": "file type",
      "descriptor_value": "text/plain",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "file size",
      "descriptor_value": "14283",
      "matches_content": true
    },
    {
      "descriptor": "measured_variable",
      "descriptor_value": "Gemeinde, Wohnungsbau, Stadtleben und Landleben",
      "matches_content": true
    }
  ],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	1	2	
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata	1	3	
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata	1	3	

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
INFO	Number of data content URI(s) specified -: 1
INFO	Selected content file to be analyzed - https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
INFO	Successfully parsed data object file using TIKa
INFO	File request status code -: 200
INFO	Successfully parsed data file(s) - https://www.<anonymous_server>.geis.org/doi/api/retrieve?pid=doi:10.4232/1.1305
SUCCESS	Found measured variables or observations (aka parameters) as content descriptor
SUCCESS	Found specified measured variable in data object content

Accessible

FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.

FAIR level: 2 of 3

moderate

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "access_details": {
    "access_condition": "unrestricted",
    "accessible_free": true
  },
  "access_level": "public"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-A1-01M-1	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	0.5	1	
FsF-A1-01M-2	Data access information is machine readable			
FsF-A1-01M-3	Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms	0.5	2	

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Access information specified -: unrestricted
INFO	Verify name through SPDX registry -: unrestricted
INFO	Found access rights information in dedicated metadata element
INFO	Used 'schema.org/isAccessibleForFree' to determine the access level (either public or restricted)
SUCCESS	Access level to data could successfully be determined -: public

FAIR level: ⓘ	initial
Resource PID/URL:	10.4232/1.1305
DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213
Software version:	2.2.1
Download assessment results:	(JSON)
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

	Score earned:		Fair level:
Findable:	6 of 7	🔄	moderate
Accessible:	1.5 of 3	🔄	initial
Interoperable:	1 of 4	🔄	initial
Reusable:	3 of 10	🔄	initial

Report:

Findable

- FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. ✅ ⌵
- FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier. ✅ ⌵
- FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability. ✅ ⌵
- FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. ❓ ⬆️

FAIR level:	0 of 3	incomplete															
Score:	0 of 1																
Output:	<pre>{ "object_content_identifier_included": [] }</pre>																
Metric tests:	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Test:</th> <th>Test name:</th> <th>Score:</th> <th>Maturity:</th> <th>Result:</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FsF-F3-01M-1</td> <td>Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">❓</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FsF-F3-01M-2</td> <td>Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">❓</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:	FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)			❓	FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content			❓	
Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:													
FsF-F3-01M-1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)			❓													
FsF-F3-01M-2	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content			❓													
Debug messages:	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Level:</th> <th>Message:</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr style="background-color: #fff9c4;"> <td>WARNING</td> <td>Data (content) identifier is missing.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Level:	Message:	WARNING	Data (content) identifier is missing.											
Level:	Message:																
WARNING	Data (content) identifier is missing.																

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 1 of 3 initial

Score: 1 of 4

Output:

```
{
  "data_content_descriptor": [],
  "object_type": "dataset"
}
```

Metric tests:	Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
	FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
	a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata			
	b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
	FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata			
	a	File size and type information are specified in metadata			
	b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata			
	FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata			
	FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: True
SUCCESS	Resource type specified -: dataset
WARNING	NO data object content available/accessible to perform file descriptors (type and size) tests
WARNING	NO measured variables found in metadata, skip 'measured_variable' test.
WARNING	Measured variables given in metadata do not match data object content

FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.

FAIR level: 1 of 3 initial

Score: 0.5 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "access_details": {
    "access_condition": "Alle im GESIS DBK ver\u00f6ffentlichten Metadaten sind frei verf\u00fcbar unter den Creative Commons
  },
  "access_level": null
}
```

<
>

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-A1-01M-1	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	0.5	1	
FsF-A1-01M-2	Data access information is machine readable			
FsF-A1-01M-3	Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms			

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
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